

Improving the Knowledge Sharing Culture in a Corporate Structure

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Abstract

This paper tries to explain the various aspects of improving the Knowledge Sharing Culture (KSC) and Knowledge Management (KM) in the corporate structure and their impacts on corporate performance. KSC plays an important role in the corporate to achieve the number of objectives of the organization like competitive advantage, performance, profit, cost reduction, etc. again in addition to this by improving the KSC in the corporate structure we can gain the advantages in terms of revenue, marketing and cost of production. Again the development of KM largely depends on the organizational structure of an organization. The internal organization structure needs to be developed through the social processes of interaction and conferences, which will facilitate the accomplishment of sustainable KSC and corporate vision. The focus of managers should be on the various components of corporate culture and factors before embarking on installing and improving a sound KSC.

Introduction

In the accounting literature, assets can be classified into two types: Tangible and Intangible assets. The tangible assets are those, which are visible and have material existence. These are, for instance, land, cash, gold, machinery etc., whereas intangible assets are those which are invisible. Knowledge is one of the important intangible assets possessed by human beings. In simple terms “knowledge is nothing but experience, values, contextual information and expert insight.” The creation and dissemination of knowledge have been carried out through various institutions for the promotion of human welfare from generation to generation. These institutions are family, society, various organization group, etc. on the economic front the corporate sectors have been playing an important role in

Improving the Knowledge Sharing Culture in a Corporate Structure

enhancing the welfare of human beings by producing various goods and services by managing the most important invisible assets i.e., knowledge. Simply possessing knowledge by an organization is not enough to enhance its growth and performance unless it is properly managed or shared among its participants.

Generally speaking, Knowledge Management (KM) is a process through which organizations to generate value from their intellectual property and knowledge-based assets. KM involves the creation, dissemination, and utilization of knowledge to its optimal level. The knowledge creation model developed by Nonaka and Takeuchi (1995) puts heavy emphasis on social processes of dialogue and interaction. The two key processes in their SECI model (socialization, externalization, combination, and internalization) that emphasize the creation of knowledge are socialization and externalization in an organization.

KM could be effective in creating various benefits as, revenue growth, production innovation, enhancing customer focus, improving competitiveness and marketing both in short term and long term for a company, when the knowledge sharing culture is deeply rooted in the organizational structure of the entire company. In the era of globalization and liberalization the development of a sustainable knowledge sharing culture has become one of the most important tasks on the part corporate managers of any forward looking companies not only in advanced countries but also in developing countries like India. The managers are trying hard and investing the huge funds to nurture and build up a sustainable KSC so as to mitigate the risks involved in the increasing agency and transaction cost problems.

As it is known that the corporate structure basically consists of three important agents: Managers, Stakeholders or employees and owners. The harmony among

these agents is essential for the attainment of the corporate objectives such as profit making and higher growth. However, these objectives of a company could only be fulfilled if proper knowledge sharing culture is in place.

Significance of Culture in an organization

Culture is a term that comprises of a set of rules, norms, values, attitude, and behavior of an organization. As we know that organizations are group of individuals and communities who share some kind of common values, norms, and rules to accomplish certain objectives. Each organization has a very distinct culture which outlines how members of the organization relate to another.

Culture is important in organization because it can powerfully influence human behavior because it is extremely hard to change. It exerts its influence in numerous invisible ways—from the kind of people who get hired, to the types of questions and comments that are tolerated, the formal and informal expectations made on the staff, the focus of reward systems, how people interact, and when they ask for help. The influence of culture in a corporate organization can be understood from the following figure.

Figure1: Culture Influences Activities in all Spheres of the Organization

Source: Smith A and McKeen (2003)

It is apparent from above figure that culture is an overarching mechanism in any kind of organization whether it is corporate or any other organization, which constrains all other aspects of organizational life and limits what is considerable desirable, possible and practical to do. Needless to say, an organization's culture

is a will therefore affect its knowledge management initiatives and will predispose employees towards particular forms of behavior in knowledge-sharing.

Knowledge Sharing Culture in an Organization

As we know that the willingness to share knowledge is positively related to profitability, productivity and competitiveness and negatively related to labor cost. Some focus group believe that knowledge sharing is positively linked to growth and innovation, increased customer satisfaction, increased shareholder value and learning.

KSC is generally defined as “king of environment where individuals are willing to disseminate information regardless of size of the organization of company.” In order to do so, individuals must adhere to the norms, values, attitudes and beliefs established by the organization. We can describe the knowledge sharing culture as one where people share openly, there is a willingness to teach and mentor others, where ideas can be freely challenged and knowledge gained from other sources can be used. There is a wide agreement that the most organizational currently act as barrier to knowledge –sharing and need to change to become more supportive of it (Gupta and Govindrajana, 2000). There are four key reasons why culture is seen as being at the base of how well knowledge is shared. (DeLong and Fahey, 2000):

- Culture shapes people’s assumptions about what knowledge is important.
- Culture determines the relationship between levels of knowledge, i.e., what knowledge belongs to the organization and what to an individual.
- Culture creates a context for social interaction about knowledge, e.g., what is sensitive, how much interaction or collaboration is desirable, which actions and behavior are rewarded and punished.

- Culture shapes the creation and adoption of new knowledge.

Determinants of Successful and Sustainable KSC in Corporate Culture:

The successful implementation of knowledge management system is highly dependent on several internal critical success factors. These include the following:

1. Motivation of Employee

The successful implementation of knowledge management system is highly dependent on employees' willingness to share data. Before analyzing how to motivate employee to share data, we should start from why employees are reluctant to exchange information with one another, thus hindering a successful knowledge management system to enhance the business development of the company.

2. Job Satisfaction

Many companies are providing the incentives to the employees to protect their own knowledge, thus preventing their own motivation to share information with other colleagues. With this in mind, there must be a significant motivation to compensate their negative feelings in applying knowledge system. The most significant element that gives employees this drive would be job satisfaction. With free flow of knowledge across the enterprise, employees can be more easily learn about the most updated knowledge of customers' trends and preferences while equipping themselves with more profound personal skills. They will co-ordinate their duties more efficiently and thus obtaining more job satisfaction. In this way rather than maintaining their position in the company in fact, they are improving and developing their unique capability in the company while gaining additional job satisfaction.

3. Promoting the Teamwork

Today, especially service sector, require timely information for performing their job responsibilities. In today's fast changing world, employees are highly motivated to share information in the shortest possible time period. Through encouraging the teamwork, management helps to create trust and eliminate employees' defensive and feeling of insecurity among one another. Thus, feeling of team spirit will be the main element to encourage employees to comply with the application of knowledge management system, with employees heading towards the same company goals and objectives in this way social capital will be created as knowledge management helps to create greater potential for employee performance improvement. It is therefore valuable for management to think deeply on how to encourage employees to share the knowledge.

4. Company Culture

After employees are motivated to data sharing, the implementation of a good a good knowledge management system largely dependent on the overall company culture. Cultural values for knowledge management are "openness and honest, sincere service attitude toward membership," and a "high trust culture for shared learning" regardless the type of organizational culture, the knowledge management system must match the culture for knowledge sharing to be used efficiently.

5. Reward for Knowledge Sharing

In most of the companies, the employees can benefit by hoarding what they know. However hoarding knowledge may then lead to duplication of work and create internal conflicts for the employees. Besides, many companies are littered with technology projects of knowledge management systems, which failed finally because their employees just didn't use them. Therefore getting employees to share knowledge is an important issue in knowledge management. For

encouraging the employees to participate and share the knowledge two types of reward system must be implemented on the bases of the performance of the employee. For the successful implementation of knowledge sharing culture in the performance appraisal form the suitable rating must be given for knowledge creating and knowledge sharing.

6. Appointment of Chief Knowledge Officer (CKO)

Why is it necessary to appoint a CKO? Knowledge sharing is critical in a knowledge-based industry, and consequently the need to have a dedicated knowledge management team headed by a CKO. “A CKO is a catalyst for knowledge-sharing. He facilitates identifying, capturing, evaluating, sharing, leveraging and creating new enterprise knowledge assets—both explicit and tacit. If one wants to make full use of all the information generated by an organization, the perceptives and actions have to change dramatically. Corporations must communicate information in a compelling way that encourages the people to recognize and use it. So, it is good to have a CKO or someone to champion the knowledge management cause and that needs to revise its rewards system to encourage the knowledge sharing.

7. Recognition of Company Value and Vision

Companies that successfully manage their tacit knowledge realize that values and vision are fundamental to determining what a firm believes to have a value. A firm's values are major determinants of what it holds to be of value. Once the firm's values are known, it becomes possible to know how a firm should value a item. When firm's knowledge is aligned with its vision and strategy, the roles of knowledge may become known, and their value measurable. The ability to produce, to respond, to anticipate, to create, to learn and to last. Creating these

abilities implies a new breed of organization. An organization that is effective and efficient in building knowledge and adding value to both company and individuals.

8. Linkage with Business Strategy

It is known that km is nothing but about enhancing organizational effectiveness and contributing to company's vitality and success. If knowledge creation is to be successfully directed, there must be an indisputable link between business strategy and knowledge management strategy. An effective knowledge management strategy is not simply a strategy but a well-balanced mix of technology, cultural change, new reward systems and business focus that is perfectly in the step with the company's business strategy.

9. Information Technology

Knowledge management in general a term is the acquiring, storing and retrieving of knowledge. Knowledge starts off in tacit form and can be transferred to other individuals in this form. Again, knowledge needs to be transformed into an explicit form to be stored and later retrieved. Here, there are so many difficulties in this transformation process especially the capturing the knowledge accurately and then representing it in an understandable form. Information technology provides tools, which can help to solve some of these issues, which are as follows:

- Supportive Information and Guidance
- Web as an Interface
- Flash as an Interface

Suggestions to improve KSC

As we know that KSC has exist in every organization to some extent irrespective of their size and nature. But in some organizations, managers are quite proactive as

Improving the Knowledge Sharing Culture in a Corporate Structure

analyses in the study of Desai (2002) in improving KSC with a zeal to reap greater benefits in the competitive market situation against the back drop of globalization and liberalization world over where most of the economies, whether rich or poor, are integrated in terms of economics, business trade and culture. The managers of an organization have to place emphasis on motivating knowledge sharing behavior in order to improve and install a sound KSC. To improve KSC in a corporate structure, the following important factors should be given more emphasis by the managers while chalking out the strategies and policies.

Figure 2: Creating a knowledge Sharing Culture

➤ Stress the need to share

First of all the stress on the need to share may seem elementary in this case and is often overlooked, but this aspect is one of the most important aspects in ensuring sound information sharing culture within the organization. From the moment an individual is brought into knowledge management, he or she would know the importance of sharing the right information with the right people. With sharing being a norm for companies that depend on information to make sound business decisions, knowledge workers must be prepared to disseminate relevant data on an ad hoc basis. To do so, they should: 1) know how knowledge sharing has

helped the company in the past through the use of case studies and best practices report, 2) be trained on the tool used to share information within the company, 3) be provided with a “cause-and –related analysis” of disseminating information when it is needed, and 4) be rewarded when information is shared.

➤ **Promoting Trust**

Promoting the trust among the members of the organization is the most crucial element behind a solid KSC. If there is a lack of trust within the company among personnel, knowledge will be hoarded. Information that is in the hands of a few individuals can be dangerous. When only a few selected have access to knowledge, they become powerful individuals in the company and can influence decisions that are made by top management. So, to avoid these situation managers must promote an environment where knowledge workers can trust their colleagues regarding what they have discovered and analyzed. Adopting the strategies such as, selecting the right people, free access of information to colleagues, and participating in team building exercise can build this kind of environment.

➤ **Beware of Information Overload**

Information overload can hinder knowledge sharing culture. With the enormous amount of data flowing in to a company and the limited amount of time that knowledge workers have per day, there is a limit to how much an individual can disseminate. Being overloaded information can cause individuals to share the bare minimum, while leaving the rest of the data in e-mails and databases. As a result, vital information will be held back from the individuals who need easy access to it. Thus, the information culture will remain unaffected.

➤ **Have the correct Tools**

In order to make individuals contribute to a culture that promotes knowledge sharing, they must be given the right tools to deliver data within the company. By listening to the needs of the knowledge workers, managers should be able to evaluate what is needed to transform their department into an efficient unit that transfers data with a few clicks of a mouse. To ensure that individuals who will be sharing information throughout the company utilize the right tools, managers should consider.

- ❑ Investigating which of the present tools in the company are being used to share information.
- ❑ Discovering how the present tools can be used more efficiently to make information accessible.
- ❑ Continuing to obtain the best possible tools to assist individuals in their work of providing data to key decision makers.
- ❑ Finding the tools that will be the right fit for with its users for the long term
- ❑ Training personnel to use the application to execute sharing tasks efficiently.

➤ **Changing the Sharers**

The last option on the part of the managers of improving KSC is to go for changing the sharers. If the situation should arise that individual(s) in the department are hindering the flow of data in the company, managers have the power to replace the individual(s). With sustained claims, personnel can be repositioned within the department to ensure that the skilled individuals who are motivated to share are in

Improving the Knowledge Sharing Culture in a Corporate Structure

the right place. Changing the sharers will breathe new life into the knowledge management unit and hopefully bring new ideas to the employees.

The improvement in the KSC is a long-term process in a corporate organization. The managers should be alert and cautious about the existing environment of the business unit while considering any important strategies pertaining to KM through improving KSC. The above suggestions should be taken into account for the fast improvement in the KSC in the organization. Moreover, the improvements of KSC depends very much on the culture of the organization rather than only on the technology. The managers should develop the internal cultures such as social, organizational, managerial and technical cultures, of a involved in the KSC can be minimized. A company can easily accomplish its desired goals such as, higher growth, competitive advantage, employee development etc., if it has an improved KSC in its structure.

Conclusion

Today, installing a knowledge sharing culture is a challenge for even the most knowledge-savvy organizations in spite of having access to other latest and the best forms of information technology. Because technology is not the only one thing by which a manager could build up a sustainable KSC in the corporate structure. Rather it is corporate culture, which plays a very significant role in installing a KM through a sound KSC. Again, the factors motivating a successful knowledge sharing culture should be given equal priority and thrust while outlining the strategies for installing a successful and sustainable KM in a corporate structure. Successful KM in any firm is a means rather than ends to increase its performance in the highly competitive business world compared to its competitors. To conclude,

Improving the Knowledge Sharing Culture in a Corporate Structure

a firm based upon the successful KM through sound KSC could easily reap the benefits of higher revenue growth, higher growth, competitive advantage, marketing advantage, employee development etc. in contrast to the firms not having a sound KSC in the present era of globalization and liberalization.

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Improving the Knowledge Sharing Culture in a Corporate Structure

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